

NDC ASPECTS

Report on Sectoral Conversations Methodology (Deliverable 1.2)

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Preface

The NDC ASPECTS project will provide inputs to the Global Stocktake under the Paris Agreement (PA) and support the potential revision of existing Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs) of the PA's parties, as well as development of new NDCs for the post 2030 period. The project will focus on four sectoral systems that are highly relevant in terms of the greenhouse gas emissions they produce yet have thus far made only limited progress in decarbonization. To advance these transformations will require to understand and leverage the Eigenlogic of those systems and take into account specific transformation challenges. These sectors are transport & mobility (land-based transport and international aviation & shipping), emission intensive industries, buildings, and agriculture, forestry & land-use, including their supply by and interaction with the energy conversion sector.

1. Changes with respect to the DoA

The work was implemented without changes to the DoA.

2. Dissemination and uptake

The deliverable is designated to an academic audience. It is structured as a report that can be submitted as an academic journal article thus becoming available to a wider audience of transdisciplinary sustainability researchers. Moreover, the manuscript contains practical guidebook and templates to support other researchers in replicating the Sectoral Conversations approach in subsequent research activities.

3. Short Summary of results

This report reflects on the operationalization of sectoral conversations approach which guided the design of the NDC Aspects project. In this way the project acts as a case study of research that aim at integrating science expertise into sustainability governance processes at global levels. Thus, the central aim of the study is to assess how and to what extent the sectoral conversation approach has fostered dialogue and learning among researchers and between researchers and stakeholders. For that aim two strands of analysis are proposed. The first reflects on the evolution of the sectoral conversations that were undertaken along the whole project duration. The second strand of analysis focuses on the structure of the academic research tasks and traces the interactions that were promoted across them. Based on the results lessons learned are extracted that offer guidance about central aspects that should be taken into account in order to promote the effective integration of science in global sustainability governance.

4. Evidence of accomplishment

This report

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Executive Summary

This report reflects on the operationalization of sectoral conversations approach which guided the design of the NDC Aspects project. In this way the NDC Aspects project acts as a case study of research that aim at integrating science expertise into sustainability governance processes at global levels. The central aim of the study is to assess how and to what extent the sectoral conversation approach has fostered dialogue and learning among researchers and between researchers and stakeholders.

Strategies for integrating science in sustainability governance

Different alternative modes of research have been debated and practised in the last decades offering options for integrating science expertise in sustainability governance processes. For the aim of the present study the focus is set on the broad strategies that are being applied in order to integrate science into sustainability governance at global levels. Zeigermann (2021) analyses how science-based networks pursue the integration process in sustainability politics and postulates two types of strategies that can be applied to organise the integration of scientific knowledge: The ‘entrepreneurial’ strategy “seeks to influence political agendas and transformations directly and proactive”, while the ‘mediating’ strategy focuses on providing policy makers with “the full suite of scientific knowledge that is presently available, and that could be used to inform a specific decision-making process”. A third possible strategy for integrating science in sustainability governance could be labelled as ‘collaborative knowledge production’, which implies two main characteristics: a) Considering the involvement of stakeholders along the whole research process, from the definition of the problem until the publication and exploitation of results (Scholz & Steiner, 2015). b) The building of spaces in which differences between the actors involved in the process are explicitly recognized and their potentials are brought to fruition.

Challenges in integrating science in global sustainability governance

It is rather straight forward to associate the mediating and entrepreneurial strategies with well-known processes and practices in global sustainability governance processes such as the climate regime. That is not the case with the collaborative knowledge production strategy. While this strategy has become increasingly applied in the field of sustainability science, most of those research experiences focus on rather small-scale cases. Based on available reflections about collaborative knowledge production projects, four types of divides can be identified as particularly challenging for promoting science integration at global levels of governance:

- Scales and levels: The multiplicity of scales at which sustainability problems can be addressed as well as the hierarchical organisation (levels) of both ecological as well as social systems.
- Epistemic: the differences in the way that knowledge is generated and interpreted in each discipline and profession, which includes differences in terminology, methods, assumptions as well as metrics that are applied to define, represent and tackle a problem or situation.
- Norms and values: the set of conceptions about what is preferred or desirable (values) and about the legitimate means of pursuing valued ends (norms).
- Organisational: the different logics or ways in which organisations manage the activities of the actors affiliated to them.

The sectoral conversation approach

A sectoral conversation approach is proposed in order to promote the systematic articulation

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between the different perspectives, levels and epistemic divides from which the overarching goal of raising the ambition of NDCs can be approached. Sectoral conversations are conceived as spaces for inter- and transdisciplinary mutual learning, in which the exchange and co-production of knowledge about the decarbonisation of one sector is fostered among NDC ASPECTS researchers and between them and (project-external) stakeholders. Moreover, the regularity of the interactions should also help in building trustful relationships between the participants of the sectoral conversations.

Methodology for tracing and reflecting exchanges and learning processes

In order to assess how the sectoral conversation approach fostered dialogue and learning along the project duration two strands of analysis are proposed. The first reflects on the evolution of the sectoral conversations that were undertaken along the whole project duration. The second strand of analysis focuses on the structure of the academic research tasks and traces the interactions that were promoted across them.

Learning from the evolution of the sectoral conversation

The original idea of conceiving the process in a sequence of three cycles could be operationalized in a productive way by all the sectors. The purpose of the first cycle might be labelled as “setting the scene”. The general purpose of the second cycle might be labelled “discussing interim results”. Finally, the third cycle was mainly used as an opportunity for “disseminating key findings” of the research process. One crucial aspect in the operationalization of the approach is the consolidation of one (or two) topics that provided the focus around which the engagements between project researchers and external stakeholders are organised. Another important aspect is the building of a balanced group of stakeholders in terms of the geographic diversity and constituencies represented in governance processes of relevance for the targeted sectors. One possible way to ensure the linkages to governance processes is to plan and to organise knowledge exchanges with stakeholders within the frame of relevant international fora. Finally, another interesting observation is the planning of several exchanges and the application of different formats within one single cycle. For instance, bilateral interactions space for deeper exploration of specific issues. Moreover, planning separate interactions with different types of actors can help to secure the engagement of stakeholders who might represent antagonistic positions.

Learning from the project design around the sectoral conversations

Overall, the combination of a) a sectoral approach that structures the different academic research tasks and b) regular spaces for knowledge exchange with key stakeholders of the targeted sectors ensured the production and dissemination of knowledge on relevant issues for advancing the decarbonisation of those sectors. Three aspects can be highlighted as key in order to bring this combination to fruitful results:

- The balance between structure and flexibility: The rather loose framework of the sectoral conversation process provided a flexible room for exploring ways to better align ongoing relevant governance debates with the predefined areas of study within the academic research tasks, and this in a sector-by-sector basis.
- The different functions of sectoral leaders: Three function can be distinguished: Sectoral leaders provided policy orientation by guiding conversations to align with ongoing political debates; they acted also as facilitators of a participatory process that connects stakeholders and researchers; and finally they were expected to establish project internal communication channels.

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- The balance between reducing complexity and maintaining explanatory value: The challenge of prioritisation and complexity reduction can be addressed in very different ways – ranging from ex-ante focus on specific sub-industries to extensive bilateral communications with leading sectoral actors.

General lessons and recommendations

We identified three main conditions for successful integration of science expertise in global sustainability governance: i) implementing Sectoral Conversations requires a project design that provides enough flexibility to explore new research avenues emerging from knowledge integration, and this in turn implies designs that are more resource-intensive than conventional research projects. ii) Setting up sectoral conversations and establishing trust takes time. iii) Effective integration of science expertise in global governance processes requires strong leadership and specific skill sets. Ideal leaders provide policy orientation, facilitate participatory processes, and manage information flow across research teams.

To address these challenges and build on the success of Sectoral Conversations, we propose the establishment of transdisciplinary fora at the program level. These fora could provide the necessary infrastructure and leadership to foster ongoing transdisciplinary research efforts.

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1 Introduction

Scientific expertise is increasingly recognized as an important component in global governance processes for sustainable development. Already the Agenda 21 adopted by the United Nations in Rio in 1992 called for “more interdisciplinary studies developed between the scientific and technological community and policy makers and with the general public to provide leadership and practical know-how to the concept of sustainable development” (United Nations, 1992). In terms of sustainability governance, particularly this ‘practical know-how’ is crucial i.e., knowledge about how to achieve deliberate changes that bring the development of societies and economies into sustainable paths. In the last decades transdisciplinarity has been debated and practised as an alternative mode of research, which is able to promote collaborations between science and other domains of society to produce such type of practical knowledge (De Jong et al., 2016; Lang et al., 2012; Scholz & Steiner, 2015). However, most of the literature on transdisciplinary research for sustainability focuses on small-scale cases i.e., projects in which teams of academic researchers collaborate with local actors (often involving not only policy makers but civil society organisations, indigenous people, private companies, among others) for addressing specific sustainability issues of rather small geographical areas (e.g. cities, watersheds, landscapes) and at small administrative scales (Bergmann et al., 2021; Shrivastava et al., 2020). Thus, while the growing experiences of transdisciplinary research for sustainability provide valuable examples and guidelines on how the interaction between science and society can be shaped locally, there is still much less experience and reflection on how to reach deeper integration of science expertise in sustainability governance processes of global scale. This study presents and reflects the experience of an international cooperation research that aimed at generating practical know-how within the frame of a global sustainability governance process.

More specifically the study focuses on the structure and the development of the research project entitled “Assessing Sectoral Perspectives on Climate Transitions to Support the Global Stocktake and Subsequent NDCs” (NDC ASPECTS). The project had the overarching objective of providing inputs to the global stocktake (GST) and support the upgrading and gender-responsive revision of existing nationally determined contributions (NDCs), as well as the development of new NDCs for the post-2030 period. For advancing that objective the project focussed particularly on four sectoral systems that are highly relevant in terms of the greenhouse gas emissions they produce, but which have so far made only limited progress in decarbonization. Thus, the research has been conceived with the explicit purpose of contributing to one of the central governance processes within the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC), which in turn is one of the most crucial global governance regimes for sustainable development today. In order to advance that purpose a sectoral approach was proposed for designing the research project. This means that the research process was structured around sectoral conversations, which provided spaces for facilitating exchange and mutual learning among scientist of different disciplines and among scientists and sectoral stakeholders. Each of these inter- and transdisciplinary exchange spaces were conceived in order to promote the systematic identification and analysis of transformation opportunities, challenges and trade-offs of one particular sector. Therefore, focusing on the NDC ASPECTS project, the aim of this study is to assess how and to what extent the sectoral conversation approach has fostered dialogue and learning among researchers and between researchers and stakeholders.

The rest of the study progresses in the following way: The second section briefly introduce some notions that can help in understanding how the integration of science expertise in global governance process can take place and which challenges are linked to that purpose. The third section introduces

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the case of study, i.e., the NDC Aspects project. Here the focus is set on the sectoral conversation approach and how it was reflected in the design of the project. The fourth describes the methodology that was applied in order to advance the aim of the study, which comprise two strands of analysis: one that is based individual and group reflections of the evolution of the sectoral conversations and another one that aims at tracing the interactions among the academic researchers within the project. The fifth section presents the results of these two strands of analysis. The sixth section review the results in order to extract more generalizable lessons about crucial aspects that promoted and/or hindered the effective integration of science expertise in the global governance processes tackled by the project. The final section summarizes the main insights generated by the study.

2 Science and global sustainability governance

The increasing relevance of sustainability at international political arenas during the 1980s and 1990s brought about also the debate about the role of science in the quest for shaping sustainable development (WBGU, 1996). This is not to say that science was absent from the sustainability debates until then. On the contrary, science has been key in shaping the sustainability discourse from its beginning. The work of the so-called 'Club of Rome' during the 1970s is probably paradigmatic for the role that science had (and still has) in describing the deep interaction between the global economic dynamics and the – at that time – already evident acceleration of ecological degradation patterns (Meadows & Club of Rome, 1972; Mesarović & Pestel, 1974). However, it is around the turn of the century that the attention shifts to the role that science can (or should) assume in building solutions and shaping the way towards sustainable development (Gibbons, 1999; Kates et al., 2001). Thus, the focus shifted from explaining (un)sustainable patterns to the possible contribution of science in governing the transition i.e., in making decisions and initiating dynamics that bring societies into sustainable development paths. This questioning added to other strands of critical enquiries on science's role in society, like those coming from the science and technology studies that questioned the naturalised assumption of science as a domain completely separated of society (Gibbons et al., 1994; Latour, 1999) or those inquiring on how the claim of value-neutrality and objectivity of science leads to positions that support the status quo and hamper the deeper understanding of the needed social transformations (Fals Borda, 2001). Different alternative modes of research have been debated and practised in the last decades offering options for integrating science expertise in sustainability governance processes, for instance: sustainability science (Kates et al., 2001), mode 2 (Gibbons et al., 1994), post-normal science (Funtowicz & Ravetz, 1993), transdisciplinarity (Klein, 2014; Scholz & Steiner, 2015) and integration and implementation sciences (Bammer et al., 2005). An analysis of the characteristics of each of these modes of research is out of the scope of this study (an attempt of comprehensive review can be found in (Fazey et al., 2018)). For the aim of the present study the focus is set on the broad strategies that are being applied in order to integrate science into sustainability governance and on lessons about the challenges that arise when pursuing integration in governance at global levels.

2.1 Conceptualising the integration of science in sustainability governance

The notion of 'integration' implies some type of boundaries between science and the domain of sustainability governance. A simple model for approaching this issue is offered by Böcher (2016) who postulates a domain of the research process (R) in which scientific evidence is produced and a domain of the political processes in which that evidence is expected to find its utilisation (U). However, recognising that “[b]etween the two spheres there is no ‘automatic’ connection that leads to a linear application of science in policy making” (Böcher, 2016), a third and intermediary process of integration (I) is needed. This third process implies a bi-directional exchange in which – on the one hand – scientific results “are selected using criteria based on practical demands” of the political actors, while practical demands from political processes “are interpreted and transformed into scientific research questions” (ibid). Based on this model – abbreviated as the 'RIU model' – Zeigermann (2021) analyses how science-based networks pursue the integration process in sustainability politics and postulates two types of strategies that can be applied to organise the

integration of scientific knowledge: The ‘entrepreneurial’ strategy “seeks to influence political agendas and transformations directly and proactive”, while the ‘mediating’ strategy focuses on providing policy makers with “the full suite of scientific knowledge that is presently available, and that could be used to inform a specific decision-making process” (Zeigermann, 2021). Within the global climate regime, the mediating strategy is exemplarily illustrated by the work of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC). Particularly its regular ‘assessment report’ that “summarises the state of knowledge of climate change, its widespread impacts and risks, and climate change mitigation and adaptation” (IPCC, 2023) can be conceptualised as a paradigmatic type of a mediating strategy of integration. In contrast, an entrepreneurial strategy comprises the derivation of specific recommendations and advice directed to actors within the political domain that are more likely to adopt and use them in the political processes (Zeigermann, 2021). In the international climate regime the entrepreneurial strategy can be illustrated by the increasing participation of and collaboration among Non-State-Actors¹ (NSA) in organising side events within the frame of the yearly conference of parties (COP) (Swarnakar et al., 2022). Within the diverse group of organisations gathered under NSA, research actors are considered to play an important role in delivering some of the main governance functions of such side events, such as capacity building and the introduction of new relevant topics that are still not present in the formal negotiations (Hjerpe & Linnér, 2010). Particularly their competences “in providing expertise, evaluating consequences, and proposing solutions” are clearly appreciated by all other actors within the climate regime (Nasiritousi et al., 2016).

Based on the RIU model it is possible to understand some ways in which integration of science expertise in sustainability governance can be pursued. However, this model still relies on assuming a complete separation between the science domain and society. This is particularly problematic when the purpose is finding ways in which science can effectively contribute to acting upon the high grade of complexity and uncertainties that are characteristic to the sustainability problems of our time. Under such conditions it is not necessarily ‘reliable knowledge’ what is being needed, but rather ‘socially and culturally robust’ i.e., knowledge that can be understood, processed and applied by all parties involved in the quest for sustainability (Gibbons et al., 1994; Scholz et al., 2006), and knowledge that accounts for the uncertainties and the ambiguities inherent to it (Vilsmaier, 2017). At least two critical issues arise from this shift of expectations. On the one hand, the continuously growing specialisation of science and corresponding fragmentation of disciplines point at the importance of integration – not only into politics but also – within the science domain itself. Thus, interdisciplinary forms of research are central here i.e., collaboration processes in which disciplinary boundary crossing is promoted. The result of the cross-fertilization among disciplines can range “from assimilating approaches borrowed from other disciplines to formation of [completely new] interdisciplinary fields” (Klein & Philipp, 2023). On the other hand, research collaborations that include the expertise of non-science actors are needed in order to ensure that knowledge from relevant actors related to the sustainability problem are incorporated and that the proposed alternatives for moving towards sustainability respond to a shared basis of norms and values about the desirable future (Lang et al., 2012).

Thus, besides the ‘entrepreneurial’ and ‘mediating’ strategies discussed before, a third possible strategy for integrating science in sustainability governance could be labelled as collaborative

¹ The notion of ‘Non-State-Actors’ is commonly used to refer to actors or entities that do not represent government or state entities but who have the ability to contribute to advance the objectives of the UNFCCC. The notion gathers a variety of actors such as non-governmental organizations, research institutions and the private sector.

knowledge production. In the last two or three decades, transdisciplinary research has been discussed and practised as an alternative for organising “collaborations among scientists from different disciplines and non-academic stakeholders from business, government, and the civil society in order to address sustainability challenges and develop solution options” (Lang et al., 2012). There is hardly one single universally accepted definition of transdisciplinarity (Vilsmäier et al., 2023). However, the conceptions of transdisciplinarity that set the focus on understanding and acting upon boundaries are of particular relevance for the present study. In this line of thinking, transdisciplinary research processes are understood as “spaces that are created between established institutions, communities and cultures” (Vilsmäier, 2017). In this conception integration does not occur after the research has delivered its product i.e., scientific knowledge. Rather, integration is a constitutive part of the research process itself. This type of collaborative strategy for integration opens or expands the questions on the involvement of non-science actors (referred also as stakeholders) and on the way of dealing with the boundaries (not only between science and society, but between different epistemic and institutional divides).

On the one hand, collaborative knowledge production implies the involvement of stakeholders along the whole research process, from the definition of the problem until the publication and exploitation of results (Scholz & Steiner, 2015). However, the intensity of that involvement can vary in the different phases of the process. For instance, while stakeholders’ knowledge and expertise are regarded as crucial for problem definition (Jahn et al., 2012), its role in building conceptual models and analysis of data can be less intensive (Stauffacher et al., 2008). On the other hand, the conception of integration as constitutive to spaces for collaborative knowledge production implies an explicit recognition of differences between the actors involved in the process. Jahn et al. (2012) point at three levels at which those differences can be found: a) the epistemic level includes the methods, assumptions and concepts upon which disciplinary or professional knowledge is produced; b) the social-organisational level points at the variety of interests and possible connections (and disconnections) among different organisational units, for instance among public institutions, within academia or also among private companies and sectors and c) the communicative level refers to different vocabulary and terminology as well as communicative practices.

2.2 Challenges of science integration in governance at global level

As briefly described in the previous section, it is rather straight forward to associate the mediating and entrepreneurial strategies with well-known processes and practices in global sustainability governance processes such as the climate regime. That is not the case with the collaborative knowledge production strategy. While this strategy has become increasingly applied in the field of sustainability science, most of those research experiences focus on rather small-scale cases, in which academic researchers collaborate with local actors for addressing specific sustainability issues of rather small geographical areas (e.g. cities, watersheds, landscapes) and at small administrative scales (e.g. municipalities, subnational administration entities) (Bergmann et al., 2021; Shrivastava et al., 2020). The growing amount of research experiences indicates that collaborative knowledge production can effectively promote the integration of science expertise and insights in real attempts to induce deliberate changes towards sustainable paths (Balvanera et al., 2017). Norström et al (2020) identify four principles as fundamental in order to ensure that collaborative processes generate promising outcomes for sustainability: (1) Context-based: It is important to situate the research process, i.e. to consider the particular social, economic and environmental context in which

the research is embedded. (2) Pluralistic: It is important to recognize and take advantage of the epistemic differences that were mentioned before. (3) Goal-oriented: It is important to “develop a collective understanding among all participants of the challenge(s) at hand, as well as an agreed measure of success (that is, the overarching goal)” (Norström et al., 2020, p. 186). (4) Interactive: This principle points at two central issues, the importance of achieving high level involvement of all participants (and avoiding token participation) as well as the need for shaping a process that allow for regular interactions along a rather long period, in which trust is built, which in turn is considered as a crucial precondition for achieving socially robust knowledge.

It is still less clear to which extent the collaborative knowledge production strategy can be applied at global governance levels. Reflecting in this direction Shrivastava et al. (2020) noted how the challenges of meeting the four principles are intensified when trying to apply collaborative knowledge production to global scales of governance: “Engagement must be context specific, yet it seems to be required at all levels, including globally. It must be pluralistic, yet the diversity of stakeholders even at the local level is immense, and more so for global processes. Goal-oriented science is challenging with diverse actors across scales” (Shrivastava et al., 2020, p. 332). Moreover, interactive and iterative engagement that promotes reflection and learning among globally distributed actors implies high organisational challenges, when it comes to promoting interactions in real physical spaces. But also, with the considerable increase of possibilities and use of digital tools for interaction in virtual spaces, the trust building requires the development of new communicational skills among all involved actors. The heuristic of the four principles formulated by Norström et al. can help with categorising the particular challenges that a collaborative knowledge production strategy faces when applied at global levels of governance. This can be done by shifting the attention to the ‘gaps’ or the ‘divides’ that need to be bridged in order to fulfil those principles:

- **Scales and levels:** This challenge refers to the multiplicity of scales at which sustainability problems can be addressed as well as the hierarchical organisation (levels) of both ecological as well as social systems. Moreover it points also at the complexity of those systems, which implies reciprocal interactions between levels, while – at the same time – each level features more or less independent logics and principles (Cash et al., 2006; Shrivastava et al., 2020)
- **Epistemic:** This challenge refers to the differences in the way that knowledge is generated and interpreted in each discipline and profession, which includes differences in terminology, methods, assumptions as well as metrics that are applied to define, represent and tackle a problem or situation (Blythe et al., 2017; Jahn et al., 2012).
- **Norms and values:** Developing a mutual understanding about the overarching goal of a governance process implies the attempt for closing the gaps between the normative systems among the actors involved in the situation; i.e. the set of conceptions about what is preferred or desirable (values) and about the legitimate means of pursuing valued ends (norms) (Scott, 2001). Such normative systems vary across the several ways that individuals affiliate to social groups, such as nationality, social class, organisation, ethnicity, gender, etc. Reflecting on this particular challenge, Lawrence et al. (2022) highlight the importance of promoting the foregrounding of norms and values of participants “to ensure that space for ongoing reflection and dialogue is embedded in the process”.

- **Organisational:** achieving appropriate levels of involvement requires bridging the different logics or ways in which organisations manage the activities of the actors affiliated to them. Because from a sociological perspective, one central feature of organisations is that things and people are considered as resources that are allocated in order to achieve specific purposes, which in turn contribute to build consistency and stability to the organisation (Scott, 2001). Bridging these organisational divides has been identified as a crucial challenge in the standard literature on transdisciplinary research (Biermann et al., 2019; Lawrence et al., 2022). In collaboration processes that should involve actors across several scales and levels of governance this challenge can be expected to be even stronger.

3 The case study – the NDC Aspects project

3.1 Objectives and divides

The project “Assessing Sectoral Perspectives on Climate Transitions to Support the Global Stocktake and Subsequent NDCs” (NDC Aspects) has the overarching goal of “provid[ing] cutting-edge analysis and robust scientific evidence in support of the 2023 GST under the PA and efforts by countries to upgrade existing NDCs up to 2030, to prepare new NDCs of highest possible ambition for the period beyond 2030, in line with long-term low-emission development strategies (LEDS), and to effectively implement these NDCs.” Thus, the research process has the explicit purpose to contribute to one of the most important governance mechanisms within the international climate regime i.e., the Global Stocktake (GST). The main objects of negotiation within this process are the Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs) and the long-term low-emission development strategies (LT-LEDS), which are defined by the Parties to the Paris Agreement i.e., sovereign national states. Particularly the NDCs are in the focus of the research. For instance, some of the specific objectives of the project are a) to assess the conditions that facilitated or limited the ambition of the NDCs submitted since 2015 and b) to develop integrated sets of policy options and strategies that countries can use to enhance their NDCs.

In order to generate such type of governance-relevant insights the project adopts a sectoral approach when it comes to identifying and evaluating specific decarbonization challenges and options. While countries and their national governments are responsible for defining, implementing and evaluating aggregate NDCs, the actual greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions within a country are strongly dependent on the current shape (and future transformation) of a particular set of sectors. Each of these sectors comprises a socio-technical system that provides societal functions such as transport, electricity, raw materials, food, feed, etc. Or in other words, while countries are the Parties directly involved in the international governance regime, the actual reduction of GHG emissions strongly depends on the effective transformation of specific sectoral systems.

Therefore, the sectoral perspective proposed by the project implies to recognize that such sectoral systems are ensembles of actors (corporations, administrative bodies, political groups/parties, international organisations, consumers), technologies and infrastructures, institutional interactions, and the path dependencies they collectively produce. Moreover, while national governance structures might have some influence in the evolution of such systems, crucial transformation barriers and opportunities are dependent on dynamics that are beyond single national borders, such as technology development, capital flows, decision processes of multinational corporations, etc. The project focuses on four sectors: a) agriculture, forestry and other land use (AFOLU), b) buildings, c) energy-intensive industry and d) transport. The proposed research design includes: the systematic identification and analysis of decarbonisation opportunities and challenges in each of the sectors in focus, the development of global benchmarks aligned to the objective of the Paris Agreement, the derivation and modelling of compatible sectoral and national pathways, the development and assessment of policy options at national levels for leveraging decarbonization potentials and the identification of gaps and means to improve global governance.

Already at this level of the project’s goal and objectives, the diversity of divides that the project needs to bridge and articulate becomes clear: (i) The levels of governance at which the research expects to contribute i.e., governance at global (e.g., GST) and at national levels (e.g. NDCs). (ii) The divide marked by national state boundaries. (iii) The difference among the sectoral systems being

targeted. (iv) The different conceptual and methodological approaches to the decarbonisation process, from the quantitative modelling and simulation of scenarios to the qualitative assessment of policies and governance structures.

3.2 Sectoral conversation approach

A sectoral conversation approach is proposed in order to promote the systematic articulation between the different perspectives, levels and epistemic divides from which the overarching goal of raising the ambition of NDCs can be approached. The above-mentioned understanding of sectoral systems as ensembles of actors, technologies, infrastructures and institutional interactions is of great help for that articulation task. Because the dynamics of change of those systems can be understood as the result of the interaction between pressures from different sources, such as national policies, changes in global frameworks, technology developments as well as changes in other interlinked sectors, among others. Moreover, the better those pressures are aligned and coordinated the more likely a deliberate system transformation becomes (Geels & Schot, 2007; Smith et al., 2005). In terms of the research project, raising the likeliness of transformative impulses implies the articulation of knowledge about the decarbonisation of the sectoral systems originating from different perspectives, levels and epistemic divides. Therefore, sectoral conversations are conceived as spaces for inter- and transdisciplinary mutual learning, in which the exchange and co-production of knowledge about the decarbonisation of one sector is fostered among NDC ASPECTS researchers and between them and (project-external) stakeholders. Moreover, the regularity of the interactions should also help in building trustful relationships between the participants of the sectoral conversations.

Figure 1: Schematic illustration of the generic process design of the sectoral conversations.

In order to operationalize the approach, each sectoral conversation was conceived as a series of mutual learning formats. Along the whole project duration, three conversation cycles were planned for each sector, in which the systematic identification and analysis of transformation opportunities, challenges and trade-offs is undertaken, as illustrated by Figure 1. The coordination of each sectoral conversation process was assigned to one or two senior researchers, who have not only solid expertise in the academic research of the corresponding sector, but who also have a trajectory in taking part in international policy-relevant debates for that sector. The aim is that each iteration (cycle) contributes to increase the level of specificity and depth of the topics that are being addressed by the sectoral conversation. In order to 'ignite' such an iterative process an initial 'groundwork' phase was considered in which the sectoral leaders undertook a scoping analysis with two main aims: (a) to identify and prioritise issues of high relevance for advancing the international and/or regional debates on the decarbonisation of the sectors and (b) to build a team of project-

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external stakeholders who engage in the sectoral conversation process. This team was expected to cover a wide range of stakeholders in terms of geographic diversity and constituencies (policymakers, public administration, academia, industry, finance sector, civil society) as well as in terms of different sub-sectors/ sub-industries when appropriate.

Each cycle of the sectoral conversation comprised three phases: a) during the preparation of each cycle the particular purpose and objectives of the conversation cycle were defined through internal consultations among leading researchers of the project as well as through the assessment of current political debates (which in turn can include consultations with external stakeholders). In this way both, the current state of the different strands of the research project as well as the governance debates were screened and the more relevant foci were defined. Moreover, the exchange formats were designed and all the needed logistic arrangements were prepared. b) The second phase comprised the realisation of one (or a series) of events, in which the inter- and transdisciplinary exchanges are facilitated. The implementation of the exchange formats comprised also the securing of results in forms of minutes, recordings and/or any other means of documentation (depending on the formats applied). c) Finally, the results of each conversation cycle were processed with the aim of drawing specific inputs relevant for each of the research strands of the project.

Furthermore, in order to coordinate and to provide some level of comparability among the different sectoral conversations two tools were developed: a 'guidebook' which contains the conceptual and methodological foundations of the sectoral conversation approach and a 'process design document' which provides step-by-step guidance for preparing and documenting each sectoral conversation cycle. The guidebook and a process design document template are provided as annexes to this report.

4 Methodology

The central aim of this report is to assess how and to what extent the Sectoral Conversation approach has fostered dialogue and learning among researchers and between researchers and stakeholders. In order to advance that objective two strands of analysis are proposed, the first reflecting on the evolution of the sectoral conversations and the second focusing on the interactions among the academic researchers within the project.

4.1 Tracing and learning from the evolution of the sectoral conversations

The methodology applied for this strand of analysis comprised two reflection exercises, the first focusing on tracing the evolution of the sectoral conversation of each single sector and the second comprising group work discussions in order to extract lessons considering the evolution of all the four sectoral conversations.

In a first stage, the two first authors of this report reviewed all the documentation available of the sectoral conversations, mainly the different iterations of the Process Design Documents (PDDs) and the minutes of each of the cycles. Based on this review a synthesis table was prepared for each sector that shows how the sectoral conversation had been conducted, including information such as dates and locations of each of the exchanges, the stated objective and guiding questions, the participants, and formats used to foster exchange and learning. In addition, the main findings and outcomes of each round were collected, as well as information about how each cycle was linked to the others in order to identify trends, barriers and lessons learnt in the process. In a second stage dialogues with the leaders of each of the sectoral conversations were conducted in order to: (a) review and complement the information collected in the synthesis tables and (b) foster the reflection of the sectoral leaders about the evolution of each sectoral conversation in two directions: which are the main insights that emerged from the process and what are lessons learned about the sectoral conversation approach itself. Finally, the synthesis tables were used as basis for building schematic illustrations of the chronological evolution of each of the sectoral conversations (See Figures 9 to 12 in Annex 1).

In the second stage, group work discussions were organised with all the sectoral leaders as well as some of the senior researchers with leading roles in the different work packages of the project. The aim was to undertake a joint reflection of the four sectoral conversation processes and to extract lessons learned about the sectoral conversation approach. Each of the group work discussions was organised in two blocks. During the first block, and based on the synthesis tables elaborated during the previous stage, the sectoral leaders reported on the evolution of their own sectoral conversations. In the second block, an open discussion was encouraged to collectively reflect about the sectoral conversation approach, to outline the lessons learned and recommendations that could be drawn. The discussions were documented in form of detailed meeting minutes which were shared to and validated by all the participants.

4.2 Characterising interactions within the academic research project structure

This strand of the analysis aimed at understanding to which extent the design of the academic research process – which was organised around the sectoral conversations – contributed to bridge the different divides for collaborative knowledge production. For this aim also two strands of analysis are undertaken. The first one focuses on the design of the project in order to understand how the divides for collaborative knowledge production are already reflected in the academic research. The attention is set on the work package structure of the project in which the multiple and diverse academic research tasks were organized. The second strand of analysis aimed at tracing the interactions across those divides within the academic research. For that aim a project internal survey was conducted to which all researchers involved in the project were invited to participate. The survey comprises three sections. The first section contains questions in order to understand the position of each researcher in relation to the structure of the project (e.g., the tasks to which the researcher's work was focused) and the most important disciplinary concepts and methods applied in her/his work. The second section comprises questions in order to trace and evaluate the interactions that each researcher built beyond her/his own position in the project structure and beyond her/his disciplinary background. The last section aimed at collecting reflections of the researchers about the design of the project in terms of the inter- and transdisciplinary integration. This section comprised several open questions which promoted individual reflections on challenges, lessons learned and alternatives for improvement.

5 Results

5.1 Tracing the evolution of Sectoral Conversations

In the following section a brief description of the evolution of each of the sectoral conversations is provided. These descriptions are based on the data collected and synthesised in the form of schematic timelines that can be found in Annex 1 of this report.

Energy-Intensive Industry

In the case of this sector all the three cycles comprised one central virtual event in which the exchange among the researchers and stakeholders was facilitated. The virtual workshop corresponding to the first cycle took place in December 2021 and focused on defining the state of decarbonisation for this sector and identifying key challenges and strategies. Main outcomes included validation of pre-defined challenges and the exploration of possible solutions for advancing the decarbonisation of the sector. Moreover, the exchanges strengthened the recognition of the importance of taking into consideration the differences between sub-sectors (e.g., steel and cement) and between regions/countries.

The virtual event of the second cycle in June 2022 focused on challenges, strategies and best practices differentiated by regions/countries. For this aim one component of the exchange was ignited by presenting the analysis of different cases of industrial decarbonisation. Moreover, a discussion was facilitated that aimed at exploring options for improving the international governance of the sector. Main results for the research process were the validation of main challenges for decarbonization of the sector in different countries and the validation of possible solutions for some of those challenges. Moreover, the particular relevance of the steel sub-sector for most of the countries being analysed by the project backed the decision to undertake deeper analysis of this sub-sector in the subsequent research activities.

The third cycle in May 2023 consisted of a virtual exchange which focused on defining elements for ambitious NDCs. The aim was to present and discuss the main findings to a broad range of EU and international stakeholders. The main attention was given to presenting the modelling results related to industrial value chains (in particular of the steel sub-sector), and to highlighting the importance of policy instruments (at national and international levels) in order to drive or increase the decarbonization dynamic of the sector.

Agriculture, Forestry and Land-use (AFOLU)

The first cycle comprised a series of talks (both online as well as in person) with different types of stakeholders from organisations that are key for the international governance of the sector. Some of these talks took place during the COP26 in December 2021 and were facilitated by the fact that the project-internal lead of this sector is regularly invited and/or involved in the organisation of international events related to the AFOLU Sector. Some of the main results from this cycle for the project were the definition of the forest sub-sector as the main focus for the rest of the research and the recognition of the overly optimistic assumptions about the mitigation potentials of the sector as one of the main challenges for advancing the actual decarbonization of the sector.

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In the same vein as the first cycle, the second cycle took advantage of events convened by key international organisations: a series of exchanges organised in May 2022 by the Global Forest Observation Initiative and a multi-stakeholder workshop in the frame of meetings convened by the Global Carbon Fund in June 2022. In this cycle the focus on forest for the research and for the sectoral conversation was consolidated. Some of the main results of this cycle comprise more specific insights about the misalignment among different international initiatives focusing on forest as well as the recognition of the importance of aligning such international initiatives also with national interests and public policies at country levels.

The main aim of the last cycle was to contribute to bridging the different misalignments that became evident along the project. For that aim an online workshop was organised in which results of the project as well as insights from other programs were taken as the basis for exploring solutions to improving synergies and coordination among development partners, international initiatives and national governments.

Buildings

The first cycle aimed to identify key aspects or topics of the sector with a high relevance for accelerating the decarbonization of the sector. Central part of the cycle was the preparation of a virtual event that took place in December 2021. Main result of this cycle was the consolidation of two main strands of research that – with the progress of the project – became the main foci of the academic research on the building sector: a) conducting a modelling exercise of the sector in the European Union (EU) based on a participative model development approach and b) comparing existing decarbonization pathways of residential building decarbonisation in China, the EU and India.

In contrast to the first cycle, the second cycle of the sectoral conversation on buildings comprised different types of exchanges with project-external stakeholders that happened along a rather long period of time. On the one hand, one virtual workshop was organised in September 2022 in order to take a deep view on the global governance of the sector. Here key insights from the research done mainly in the WP6 were discussed, validated and/or complemented with stakeholders from international cooperation organisations and researchers from various organisations. On the other hand – and based on the results and contacts done in the first cycle – a series of bi-lateral exchanges with experts from China and India (from academia, public and private sector) were undertaken in the first quarter of 2023 in order to complement the comparative analysis between the three regions/countries mentioned before. Out of these exchanges collaborations were forged with regional experts, which went beyond the sole complementing of data and assumptions and extended into the collaborative elaboration of outputs also resulting in scientific publications.

The main component of the third cycle was a virtual workshop in February 2024. It contained two sessions, where studies focused on the EU were presented. Session 1 aimed at disseminating the study results of "Decarbonisation Pathways for the Building Sector in the EU 27" (WP3 Deliverable & Academic Manuscript) covering mitigation pathways and policy options to achieve long-term building decarbonization goals. Session 2 revolved around the gender dimension in deep renovation projects. The project team presented concepts, methodology, and interim findings to engage with the audience. Feedback received will be carefully considered and incorporated into the ongoing study.

Transport and Mobility

The transport sector featured a unique evolution. For this sector two different engagement strategies were defined around two focus topics that emerged from the groundwork at the beginning of the process in December 2021. One sectoral conversation focused on international maritime decarbonization strategies and decided to address one overlooked, but structural mitigation option which relates to the shortening and regionalisation of global supply chains. Another Sectoral Conversation focused on the decarbonization strategy of passenger mobility through shifting private mobility to smaller and lighter electric vehicles. The sectoral conversation on this second topic developed in the second half of 2023 and deployed only two cycles of exchange. For the sake of comparability, in this study we focus only on the evolution of the first topic, which ran in a more parallel fashion to the sectoral conversations of the other sectors.

In the debate on decarbonization of maritime transport three types of key actors were identified as relevant for engaging in the sectoral conversation: (a) public policy practitioners who are used to work on industrial and trade policies, (b) private company leaders who decide why and where to locate production assets and supply chain activities, and (c) various actors from academia or international organisations who play a role of influencers in the maritime decarbonization strategy debates.

The first cycle focused on engaging with public policy practitioners to test their reactions on the topic and learn from their experience on the public policy action levers, and underlying drivers of change. This knowledge exchange took the form of a closed online workshop in July 2022. The second cycle focused on engaging with IMO-UNFCCC international experts to test reactions to the first lessons and better understand how to disseminate these lessons towards other UNFCCC and IMO experts. It comprised several bilateral talks before COP27 and a dedicated side event during the COP27, in December 2022, with selected expert invitees. The third cycle focused on engaging with private company leaders. It started with first contacts in Sept and October 2022, in which it became clear that – at that time – it was not appropriate to bring all actors around the same table. Therefore, more intensive engagement was undertaken after the COP27 (during February and March 2023) through bilateral meetings or in the form of semi-structured interviews.

5.2 Similarities and differences among the four Sectoral Conversations

Figure 2 shows in a schematic and summarised way the evolution of all the four sectoral conversations that were implemented during the project. As illustrated by the previous section, the original idea of conceiving the process in a sequence of three cycles could be operationalized in a productive way by all the sectors. While the specific topics and aims of each sectoral conversation and of each cycle are very different, some interesting similarities in the general purpose of the cycles can be identified. The purpose of the first cycle might be labelled as “setting the scene” which entailed two main objectives (a) to contact and convene a group of key stakeholders from different societal domains that would engage along the sectoral conversation and at the same time (b) to validate or to consolidate the decision about where to put the main focus of the research and of the further exchanges. The exchange spaces created in the second cycle were mainly used in order to present and discuss with stakeholders the interim results from different research strands of the project. All sectoral leaders reported significant inputs from these exchanges that enriched the

ongoing research processes. The general purpose of the second cycle might be labelled “discussing interim results”. Finally, the third cycle was mainly used as an opportunity for “disseminating key findings” of the research process.

Figure 2: Schematic illustration of the chronological evolution of the four sectoral conversations, indicating exchange events in each cycle.

While all sectoral conversations feature this general pattern of evolution, there are interesting differences in the speed and way in which this pattern developed. One crucial element is the consolidation of one (or two) topics that provided the focus around which the engagements between project researchers and external stakeholders were organised. The case of the transport sector is exemplary for a process that reached a high level of specificity in a rather short time. In that case, already during the groundwork phase it was possible to define two topics with strong relevance in the global governance of the decarbonization of the sector and where the research project could provide significant inputs. Still, the first cycle was used as testing space for that starting assumption. The case of the industry sector provides a contrasting example. In this case a strong focus on the decarbonization of the global steel industry developed along the three cycles. However, while this topic got a central role, it was not the only issue within the knowledge exchanges. Other fields such as the decarbonization of industrial clusters and the cement industry were addressed during the sectoral conversation and the research process. From the perspective of the academic research process, consolidating focus topics is a strategy for reducing the complexity of the systems that are studied, which in turn allows for deeper levels of analysis. From the perspective of the integration of science expertise in global governance, this can be also understood as a strategy to deal with the challenge of bridging between different norms and values. Because finding a shared topic of concern among the different types of stakeholders facilitates not only the building of mutual understanding about goals, but also about possible and legitimated strategies to effectively advance the decarbonisation.

Another important element of the evolution pattern of the sectoral conversation is the way in which linkages to ongoing governance processes were built, to global and – in some cases also – to national levels. One strategy for building such linkages was already part of the original conception of the

sectoral conversation, which foresees a “stakeholder mapping” exercise as part of the groundwork phase (see the “process design document” in Annex 3). The aim of this exercise is to build a balanced group of stakeholders in terms of the geographic diversity and constituencies represented in governance processes of relevance for the targeted sectors. Thus, this is a common characteristic in all the four sectoral conversations which is well illustrated by the diversity of stakeholder types that were engaged along all three cycles (see the “schematic timelines” in Annex 1). Another possible way to ensure the linkages to governance processes is to plan and organise knowledge exchanges with stakeholders within the frame of relevant international fora. This strategy was particularly often deployed along the sectoral conversations of AFOLU and Transport. In both cases some of the exchange events were planned within the framework of the COPs of the UNFCCC. Moreover, some of those meetings were convened in cooperation with organisations or networks that gather specific technical expertise of the sectors, like the Global Forest Observation Initiative, the platform SLOCAT and the International Maritime Organization (IMO). In this way these sectoral conversations could take advantage of the strong convening effect of international networks, organisations and fora, which are in turn important platforms or actors in the global governance of the respective sectors. Looking through the perspective of the RIU model, these two sectoral conversations entail features of an entrepreneurial strategy, in which the exchanges with stakeholders sought to influence political agendas in direct and proactive ways.

Finally, another interesting observation is the planning of several exchanges and the application of different formats within one single cycle. For instance, three of the four sectoral conversations comprised several moments in which exchanges with only one person or with only one type of stakeholder were organised. On the one hand such bilateral interactions provided space for deeper exploration of specific issues. This was the main motivation of the bilateral exchanges applied in the case of the building sector. On the other hand, this can be helpful in order to secure the engagement of stakeholders who might represent antagonistic positions to the topic in focus and/or to the positions of other stakeholders. This has been the main purpose of planning several separated exchanges in the cases of AFOLU and transport sectors. Moreover, the evolution of the sectoral conversation on transport followed a path in which the addressing of specific types of stakeholders was explicitly planned in a separate way. In this case the insights about how to advance the decarbonisation of the maritime sector through the shortening and regionalisation of global supply chains were gradually strengthened and consolidated through iterative exchanges with different types of stakeholders. This iteration followed a pathway in which the interaction with the private sector actors – which were expected to be more reluctant to the topic in general – was planned once after having discussed and strengthened the arguments in two previous rounds with other relevant actors for the sector (policy practitioners and international influencers).

5.3 Collaborative knowledge production divides within the academic research structure

The academic research components of the projects were organised ‘around’ the sectoral conversations (As schematically illustrated in Figure 3). The insights from the different work packages were geared towards the inter- and transdisciplinary exchange spaces of the sectoral conversations, which in turn processed the different inputs in order to generate knowledge for increasing the ambition of future NDCs and improving the enabling environment at global level. Within the structure of the project, the Work Package 1 comprised all the activities aimed at preparing,

implementing and coordinating the sectoral conversations in the four targeted sectors. The academic research tasks of the project were organised in five work packages. This distribution of the research tasks mirrors three different levels of governance at which the transformation of the targeted sector can be addressed: a) At sectoral level in WP3 by conducting bottom-up analysis of potential decarbonization pathways of each of the targeted sectors, in which combinations of diverse promising socio-technical options are taken into account. b) At national level in WP5 in two main ways, by comparing the current developments in the targeted countries with alternative more ambitious national pathways that can be derived out of the analysis in WP3 and by outlining and analysing how coherent policy packages could maximise climate and broader sustainability benefits. c) At global level in WP2, by developing quantitative global scenarios with sectoral and regional resolution exploring different combinations of socio-technical alternatives, and in WP6 by identifying gaps and means to improve global governance to enhance the implementation of NDCs and enable the realisation of transformation pathways in the selected sectors. Along this ‘governance level divide’ within the project, WP4 featured a rather cross-boundary character, because while NDCs and related national policies were in focus, the aim was to assess their effectiveness in addressing the transformation of the target sectors and to identify options for improving that transformational function (e.g., effectively leveraging decarbonisation potentials of the sectors).

The work package structure also mirrors two different epistemic approaches that were applied in the project: in WP2 and WP3 quantitative models are the main tool applied in order to explore and assess the effectiveness of decarbonisation pathways. In WP4 and WP6 the focus is on the qualitative analysis of political conditions and the policy options that can guide the realisation of the pathways explored in the other work packages. Along this ‘epistemic divide’ within the project, WP5 featured a cross-boundary character, because here both types of analysis were applied in order to build and assess more ambitious national pathways.

Figure 3: Schematic illustration of the work package structure of the NDC Aspects project.

5.4 Interactions within the academic research project structure

This section presents the results of the project internal survey, which aims at characterising the interactions among the academic researchers involved in the project, which in turn provide

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indications about how the design of the project promoted the exchange and learning across the different divides that are already present in the structure of the project. A total of 21 valid responses were received. This is around one fourth of the estimated number of researchers that were active within the project during the more than 3 years of duration. Thus, the sample is not expected to be representative in the sense of describing common patterns among all the researchers. It rather provides indications about the diversity of perspectives that were present in the realisation of the project and about how those perspectives were able to exchange and learn from each other.

The first set of questions of the internal survey aimed at understanding the position of each researcher within the research structure. Table 1 summarises the main results in this regard. Within the sample a certain matching between disciplines and work package affiliations can be seen. The nine responders from the social and political sciences and the two responders from Law were mostly (or exclusively) involved in WP4 and WP6, while the five responders from the engineering disciplines were mostly involved in WP2 and WP3. The four respondents from economics were rather distributed across all work packages. This partial matching between disciplines and work packages can be expected, because of the above-mentioned division of research tasks, in which quantitative modelling is focused in WP2 and WP3, while qualitative policy analyses are mainly gathered under WP4 and WP6.

Table 1: Broader disciplinary affiliation stated by the researchers in combination with their work package affiliations (i.e., the work packages specified as the main focus of their work within the project).

Broad disciplinary field	# of researchers	Stated affiliations				
		WP2	WP3	WP4	WP5	WP6
Natural Science	1	0	1	1	0	0
Engineering	5	0	4	0	3	0
Economics	4	3	2	1	2	2
Social & Political Sciences	9	0	1	8	2	8
Law	2	0	0	1	0	2

The second set of questions aimed at getting data about exchange of knowledge and learning across the different tasks and work packages of the project. In the first place the survey asked for information to trace the exchange of knowledge across tasks and work packages. Table 2 presents a matrix that relates the work package affiliation stated by the responders with their responses about contributions that they received for their own research work from other work packages. The matrix cleans up responses about exchanges within single work packages. Thus, the matrix illustrates that the researchers experienced interactions across almost all the division lines that represent the work packages. Within the sample there is a higher concentration of contributions from WP3, followed by contributions from WP4 and WP2. This result seems to reflect the central role that WP3 and WP4 had in the whole research process, because crucial information about the political and socio-technical conditions, challenges and opportunities for the decarbonization of the targeted sectors was initially collected in those work packages.

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Table 2: Stated contributions from other work packages to the research work of the responders. Stated contributions across the boundary between predominantly quantitative (WP2 and WP3) and qualitative (WP4 and WP6) research are highlighted in green.

		Sources of inputs				
		WP2	WP3	WP4	WP5	WP6
Receivers of inputs	WP2		1	1	1	0
	WP3	2		2	1	1
	WP4	3	4		2	0
	WP5	2	3	4		1
	WP6	2	4	3	2	
Total Contributions		9	12	10	6	2

Figure 4 and 5 present data about the spaces or instances in which interdisciplinary exchanges took place. The project plan explicitly foresaw two types of regular instances in which interdisciplinary exchanges were expected to be fostered: The consortium meetings, which acted as the central instance for presenting and discussing the progress of all the work packages of the project and the sectoral conversation events (each of them organised along three cycles as described in previous sections).

Besides those explicitly planned instances, regular meetings were also planned a) by work package leading teams in order to maintain a basic flow of information for researchers working in the same work packages and b) by sectoral leaders - in some cases - in order to prepare the interactions with external stakeholders at events of the sectoral conversations. Additionally, a couple of meetings were organised by leading researchers of WP3 with the aim of fostering exchange on the decarbonisation narratives and scenarios for the target sectors that were emerging along the different research strands of the project. The results in Figure 4 shows that almost all the responders participated in at least one of the consortium meetings. This seems to illustrate the centrality of this interdisciplinary exchange instance in the project design. The responders also participated in other exchange instances linked to work packages and sectoral conversations, however the difference with the stated participation to the consortium meeting is rather significant and unexpected. Because each researcher was involved in tasks of at least one work package, and most of those tasks were linked to at least one sector. Thus, we expected levels of involvement in those exchanges related to work packages and sectors to be similar (or higher) than the participation in the central consortium meetings, which were less regular and of broader scope. When asked for the exchange instance that provided the most fruitful interactions, the consortium meetings received again more responses than the work package meetings (see Figure 5). These results might point at some difficulties in establishing productive and regular interactions beyond the exchange instances that were explicitly stated in the project plan. More than half of the responders attended at least one of the meetings of the harmonisation workshop, this is an indication that more than half of the respondents were researchers with leading roles in the project as those workshops targeted leaders of work packages, and sectors.

Figure 4: Interdisciplinary exchange instances in which interaction across several research tasks took place.

Figure 5: Interdisciplinary exchange instances perceived to be fruitful.

Figures 6 and 7 present the results of questions asking for the way in which inputs from other researchers and from external stakeholders contributed to the research work of the responders. Within the sample the contributions from interdisciplinary exchanges were more often recognized as valuable than contributions from project external stakeholders. However, when significant contributions from inter- and transdisciplinary exchanges are recognized, they could be productively integrated in all stages of the analytical process, from the review of guiding questions or central assumptions up to the way in which the outcomes of the research are presented.

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Figure 6: The ways in which insights from other researchers contributed to the research work of the responders.

Figure 7: The ways in which inputs from external stakeholders contributed to the research work of the responders.

Figure 8 shows that the majority of participants who have previous experiences in being part of inter- and transdisciplinary research projects perceived that the NDC Aspects project was at least as successful as previous experiences in fostering knowledge integration. Furthermore, nine respondents consider this success to surpass the outcomes observed in preceding projects.

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Figure 8: Success of the NDC ASPECTS project in terms of Inter-/transdisciplinary Integration in comparison with previous research experiences.

The last set of questions of the survey collected individual reflections on lessons learned and challenges of facilitating inter- and transdisciplinary knowledge integration. Table 3 lists five themes that were mentioned by the respondents when asked about the specific learnings that were useful to their own research. The first two themes are observations on the general research processes. First of all, five commenters highlighted the value of learning about the differences across countries and geographical regions when it comes to determining the priorities and the way to advance decarbonization of single sectors. Another often mentioned component are the quantitative models for assessing decarbonisation paths. Mentions about models included the opportunity to apply and/or complement already available models in order to address new types of questions. Also, the possibility to learn from other modelling approaches was mentioned here.

Table 3: Themes mentioned by respondents when asked to share main lessons learned from the inter- and transdisciplinary knowledge exchanges in which they were involved.

Themes	# of comments
Different perspectives and priorities across world regions	5
Quantitative models	5
Potential of climate clubs in decarbonizing energy-intensive industries	3
The (overestimated) role of negative emissions from AFOLU	2
Options for linking global and (sub-)national governance (buildings and transport)	2

The other three themes are associated with **sector-specific lessons**. This helps researchers to gain an insider's view of how a sector works, so that the decisions to be made are adapted to that reality. For example, three respondents highlighted the insights they got about the role that so-called climate clubs can have in advancing the decarbonization of energy intensive industry. Sectoral climate clubs have been proposed to facilitate common target-setting, cooperation on setting standards for green materials and supporting technology transfer (Hermwille et al., 2022). Two respondents highlighted the insights they learned from the AFOLU sector, where the discussions had shifted their focus on the role of forests (and land use in general) from balancing competing interests to market finance and domestic use for NDC ambition in critical developing countries. Finally, two responses pointed at the

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recognition of the importance to link global governance debates to national and subnational processes. This was illustrated - for instance - by the building sector conversations where relevant potentials were identified to involve key international institutions, such as the G7/G20 or the Major Economies Forum into the building sector governance strategies.

Table 4 lists five main themes that were mentioned by the respondents when reflecting on the challenges they experienced for effectively undertaking inter- and transdisciplinary knowledge exchanges. Five respondents raised concerns about a rather sporadic or uncoordinated nature of the exchanges within and across the work packages - besides the explicitly planned consortium meetings. Three comments related this issue also with a certain disconnection of the sectoral conversations with the rest of the workstreams of the project. The comments in this respect are in line with the previous observations of relatively low levels of involvement in those exchanges linked to work packages progress and to the preparation of sectoral conversations. Another relatively prominent concern refers to difficulties in integrating quantitative and qualitative epistemic divides. Some of them indicate that the division lines among work packages - which reflected precisely that epistemic divide as mentioned before - might have hindered the deeper integration of quantitative and qualitative analytical approaches. Furthermore, time constraints, attributed to the different pace of analysis among the different sectors and work packages, were acknowledged as leading to less in-depth and integrative exchanges between work packages. Finally, two respondents highlighted the importance of quickly narrowing the focus of inter- and transdisciplinary discussions in order to take advantage of such spaces. This issue implied not only the finding of a general focus within the sectoral conversation processes but also - and foremost - the clear definition of topics to be discussed in single meetings or events.

Table 4: Themes mentioned by respondents when asked to reflect on the main challenges they experienced in undertaking inter- and transdisciplinary knowledge exchanges.

Themes	# of comments
Higher regularity of exchanges across WPs and sectors	5
Improve integration of qualitative and quantitative research streams	4
Improve connection of Sectoral Conversations to research process	3
More time for in-depth exchange	2
Quick narrowing focus of discussions	2

6 Discussion & Lessons Learned

Overall, the presented results illustrate that the sectoral conversation approach has proved to be helpful in overcoming knowledge divides and facilitating fruitful inter- and transdisciplinary collaboration. The combination of a) a sectoral approach that structures the different academic research tasks and b) regular spaces for knowledge exchange with key stakeholders of the targeted sectors ensured the production and dissemination of knowledge on relevant issues for advancing the decarbonisation of those sectors. The project design entailed diverse exchange instances targeted at promoting the interaction across different types of divides within the structure of the academic research as well as across the boundary between the research project and global governance arenas of the targeted sectors. In this way the project yielded a number of research outcomes that meet the transdisciplinary aspiration “(a) to grasp the relevant complexity of a problem (b) to take into account the diversity of life-world and scientific perceptions of problems, (c) to link abstract and case-specific knowledge, and (d) develop knowledge and practices that promote what is perceived to be the common good” (Hirsch Hadorn et al., 2008, p. 4). Moreover, some of those research outputs, with strong innovative character, were neither planned nor conceived during the proposal preparation of the project. Table 5 lists a selection of manuscripts that emerged from new forms of collaboration during the project and in our view resulted in innovative research that is highly relevant from a political and societal point of view.

Table 5: Illustrative examples of research outputs that emerged in a rather ‘organic’ way out of the inter- and transdisciplinary collaborations forged along the project.

Topic	Inclusion of Gender Dimension in Sectoral Modelling	Research on the economic and environmental effects of industrial policy nationalism	Modelling the effects of shortened value chains on international transport emissions
Description of research outputs	So far, the category of gender has been hardly operationalized within techno-economic modelling. Sectoral Conversations led to enhancing modelling tools in the transport and building sectors	During the project duration geopolitical competition over emerging green industries arose. Employing a global computational equilibrium model, researchers analysed the economic and environmental effects of trade restrictions related to industrial policy nationalism.	The transport SC focussed on the potential opportunities and trade-offs of shortening supply chains (see above). Building on this, new scenarios were developed employing the enhanced modelling tools for international maritime transport.
Main knowledge divides overcome	SCs helped to overcome predominantly epistemic and normative divides . Related to norms, the work challenges the priority that is given to gainful work over care work. An epistemic challenge is that most statistical data required for more granular and explicit gender analyses is not currently being collected systematically	SCs helped to identify this challenge early by bringing together participants from diverse organisational backgrounds . In-depth discussions helped to bridge epistemic divides between political scientists working on global politics and researchers developing detailed socio-economic modelling tools	The main divides overcome for this output are related to scales and levels and organisational dimensions . Issues of managing supply chains (re-shoring & nearshoring) were mostly discussed under a security of supply paradigm with a specific community. SCs enabled to link this debate to climate change mitigation discourse.
Reference	Forthcoming	https://ndc-aspects.eu/sites/default/files/2024-03/20240313_NDC%20ASPECTS_D6-3_paperB.pdf	NDC ASPECTS Deliverable D2.3, forthcoming

The results also provide indications of important aspects that influenced the ability to foster inter- and transdisciplinary exchange and learning, which can be grouped in three fields:

The balance between structure and flexibility

As already highlighted, the design of the project combined a rather fixed and predetermined structure of the academic research tasks (organised in the WP2 to WP6) with a rather loose framework of a process for involvement of external stakeholders (the sectoral conversations, contained in WP1). This combination seems to have helped to overcome - at least to some extent - the limitations that derive from the rigidity of predetermined research programmes. By definition, research projects need to entail a fixed budget, a project duration and a clear indication of the work programme. Within these structural limitations there is rather little room within the planned research tasks, to explore areas of interest that might emerge from the interactions with stakeholders and/or because of far-reaching perturbation in the societal fields (e.g., Russia's attack on Ukraine). The rather loose framework of the sectoral conversation process provided a flexible room for exploring ways to better align ongoing relevant governance debates with the predefined areas of study within the academic research tasks, and this in a sector-by-sector basis. However, during the group reflections with leader researchers, the limitations for properly reacting to and addressing interesting topics were often highlighted. One way to overcome this would be to establish Sectoral Conversations as a permanent research infrastructure at the programme level. The ideas and insights generated within those could then inform subsequent (smaller) individual projects. This would also help overcome another issue related to the way in which research programmes work. Setting up the Sectoral Conversations and building trust among their members requires a significant amount of time. After three years of implementing the NDC ASPECTS project, we are now at the stage where collaboration among the participants of the Sectoral Conversations has achieved a peak but the project is about to end. Consequently, lifting Sectoral Conversations to the programme level would allow individual projects to skip the first step and proceed much faster with substantive conversations.

The different functions of sectoral leaders

Sectoral leaders played an extremely important role for the operationalization of the sectoral conversation approach. In practice, we can identify three distinct functions: they provided policy orientation by guiding conversations to align with ongoing political debates, they acted also as facilitators of a participatory process that connects stakeholders and researchers, and finally they were expected to establish project internal communication channels to ensure proper information flows across work packages and the different qualitative and quantitative research teams.

To do justice to the three functions outlined above requires a high level of competence within the science domain as well as strong experience at the intersection of science and policy. However, it is also potentially an unrewarding job since it does not necessarily lead to reputational gains or concrete academic outputs. The impact is indirect since the sectoral leaders enable the participants to develop new research questions, new insights or new networks and collaborations, but very often are not directly involved in the actual research process. Thus, their work enables other people to do better research, but it is not necessarily helping the leader him or herself to excel in a way that is typically rewarded in an academic setting. In this, the role of sectoral leaders is akin to care work which is hugely important to enabling other types of work but not recognized and rewarded in the same way.

Moreover, establishing and keeping a balance between the functions is challenging. For instance, the results indicated some disconnection between the sectoral conversation process and the academic

research tasks. When reflecting on this issue during the work group discussions, it became clear that it took time for the sectoral leaders to develop the communication tools and channels not only to ensure the flow of information between the sectoral conversations and the academic research, but also to shape the interdisciplinary exchanges across the work packages.

The balance between reducing complexity and maintaining explanatory value

One of the key challenges for sectoral leaders was to reduce complexity in a way that makes the conversations concrete enough to be fruitful but not alienate external stakeholders. Reducing complexity must not come at the expense of explanatory value – mere simplification is often not conducive to generating insightful and relevant results. Instead, it requires prioritisation, but a prioritisation that is based on joined deliberations by the participants. The results illustrate that the four sectoral leaders addressed this challenge of prioritisation and complexity reduction in very different ways – ranging from ex-ante focus on specific sub-industries to extensive bilateral communications with leading sectoral actors. After intense debriefings we concluded that there is no optimal way of achieving this task. Despite very different means, we achieved similar results in terms of managing the scope of the conversations. Success here depends very much on the individual style of leadership and the networks exploited to engage stakeholders.

7 Conclusions

This study explored the effectiveness of "Sectoral Conversations" as a transdisciplinary research design for integrating knowledge across disciplines in a large EU-funded project on climate policy. Our findings demonstrate that transdisciplinary research, particularly through Sectoral Conversations, offers a powerful approach to bridge knowledge gaps and achieve successful knowledge integration. The combination of sectoral focus and dedicated spaces for knowledge exchange with stakeholders ensured the production and dissemination of policy-relevant knowledge on decarbonization across various sectors. According to our respondents, it also proved to be more effective than traditional methods employed in comparable research projects.

The approach fostered unexpected and highly valuable research outputs. The project yielded significant results beyond those initially planned, including research on integrating gender dimensions into sectoral modelling and the economic and environmental effects of industrial policy nationalism. These findings (see Table 5) exemplify the ability of Sectoral Conversations to achieve transdisciplinary research goals: grasping problem complexity, incorporating diverse perspectives, linking abstract and specific knowledge, and developing solutions for the common good.

We identified three main conditions for successful transdisciplinary knowledge integration: First, implementing Sectoral Conversations is resource-intensive. The inherent complexity of transdisciplinary research makes it challenging to precisely predict outcomes. Moreover, rigidly predetermined work programmes can limit the exploration of new research avenues emerging from knowledge integration. However, designing research projects with too much flexibility and uncertainty about the outcomes is hard to justify and typically not valued by evaluators and funders.

Secondly, setting up Sectoral Conversations and establishing trust takes time. It takes time for leaders of sectoral conversations to assume their responsibilities and leverage their networks to establish a trustful working atmosphere among the participants of the sectoral conversations. While necessary, this time invested can appear to be "unproductive" time from the point of view of other researchers involved.

And thirdly and related to the previous point, effective transdisciplinary knowledge integration requires strong leadership and specific skill sets. Ideal leaders provide policy orientation, facilitate participatory processes, and manage information flow across research teams. Leaders must manage complexity to facilitate productive discussions without compromising accuracy. Prioritisation based on joint deliberation by participants is crucial. There is no one-size-fits-all approach – successful leadership styles leverage individual strengths and existing stakeholder networks. However, the current academic reward system often undervalues these leadership qualities. We propose acknowledging the importance of "shaping" and "care work" roles in transdisciplinary research.

To address these challenges and build on the success of Sectoral Conversations, we propose the establishment of transdisciplinary fora at the program level. These fora could provide the necessary infrastructure and leadership to foster ongoing transdisciplinary research efforts. In the context of the EU Horizon Europe research programme or its successor, this could be implemented in the form of long-term Coordination and Support Activities (CSAs) which are aligned with the Multiannual Financial Framework (MFF) cycle. Such an approach would ensure continuity, facilitate the development of strong leadership skills, and ultimately contribute to more effective scientific advice for global sustainability governance processes.

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In conclusion, this study demonstrates the effectiveness of Sectoral Conversations in overcoming knowledge divides and driving transdisciplinary research in the context of global climate governance. While developed for a specific EU-funded project, the core principles of Sectoral Conversations hold promise for a wider range of transdisciplinary endeavours. By fostering collaboration and integrating diverse perspectives, Sectoral Conversations can be a valuable tool for tackling complex challenges across various disciplines and sectors, ultimately contributing to the advancement of scientific expertise in global governance processes.

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Annex 1 – Detailed Timelines of Sectoral Conversations

Figure 9: Timeline of the evolution of the sectoral conversation on AFOLU sector. Schematic illustration of the exchange events of each cycle.

Figure 10: Timeline of the evolution of the sectoral conversation on Energy-Intensive Industries sector. Schematic illustration of the exchange events of each cycle.

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Figure 11: Timeline of the evolution of the sectoral conversation on Transport and Mobility sector. Schematic illustration of the exchange events of each cycle.

Figure 12: Timeline of the evolution of the sectoral conversation on Building sector. Schematic illustration of the exchange events of each cycle.

Annex 2 – Sectoral Conversations Guidebook

Introduction

The purpose of the Sectoral Conversations is to provide a **space for inter- and transdisciplinary exchange within the project and with project-external sectoral experts**. It provides an opportunity to share results from the outset with different disciplines and external stakeholders. Their feedback might help to hone research questions and reconfigure ongoing analyses so that they speak to each other, thus maximizing their policy and academic relevance.

The Sectoral Conversations shall encourage an open and transparent research process in a trustful environment. It should NOT constrain research in any of the subsequent work packages. Nor should the other work packages focus their research activities exclusively on providing inputs to the Sectoral Conversations.

The purpose of this guidebook is to support the sectoral leads in organizing the Sectoral Conversations in a way that stimulates exchange between different disciplines in order to help us discover and exploit synergies between our respective research activities.

The guidebook is structured in three sections. After this introduction, we first introduce a selection of key terms and concepts that are the foundation of our Sectoral Conversation. Section 3 introduces the general concept of the Sectoral Conversations (SC) and how they ought to be structured. Subsequently, we provide guidance for the Sectoral Leads in charge of the implementation of the Sectoral Conversations on how to develop the groundwork for a successful implementation, including by pre-scoping the thematic focus of the SCs as well as considerations on the involvement of stakeholders. Section 4, then, can be seen as a cookbook of engagement methods that can be selected by the sectoral teams as they see fit.

Key Terms and Concepts

This section provides an overview of key scientific concepts and terms. The discussion provided represents not necessarily a definitive discussion of the term but reflects the intended use of the terms. This section is therefore a point of reference and resource, the groundwork for our common language across disciplines and sectors.

Sectoral System

The following discussion is cited from Oberthür, S., Hermwille, L., & Rayner, T. (2021). A sectoral perspective on global climate governance: Analytical foundation. Earth System Governance, 8, 100104. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.esg.2021.100104>:

According to transition theory (see also Victor et al., 2019) sectoral systems provide identifiable societal functions such as transport, electricity, or raw materials for industrial production. They are constituted of ensembles of actors (corporations, administrative bodies, political groups/parties, international organizations), technologies and infrastructures, economic structures, institutions and ideas that produce degrees of path dependency and resistance to change (Geels & Schot, 2010). Such systems are complex, which entails that (1) they can produce emergent phenomena/effects that are more than the systems' parts, and (2) they are open, i.e. closely related to and potentially

overlapping and interdependent with other sectoral systems (Page, 2011). Our societies and economies are supported by a patchwork of such socio-technological systems. Their number tends to increase with the advancing functional differentiation of modern societies, which also entails that sectoral systems might be further subdivided into various overlapping sectoral subsystems. For example, relevant transport sub-sectors include land transport (by train, car, others), sea/water transport, air transport, passenger transport, freight transport, international transport (aviation and maritime), urban transport, etc. As this example indicates, sectoral systems can easily overlap (e.g., urban transport and passenger/ freight transport) (Borrás & Edler, 2014; Harich, 2010; Page, 2011; Schot & Kanger, 2018; Unruh, 2000).

Sectoral Conversations

There is increasing consensus that cooperation between scientists from different disciplines and actors from outside academia is needed in order to deal with the urgent sustainability challenges faced by the modern global world (Bammer, 2005; Hirsch Hadorn et al., 2008; Jahn & Keil, 2012; Scholz, 2000).

A key challenge is to advance the knowledge articulation across the different epistemic cultures, levels and scales that have to be necessarily addressed by transformative dynamics towards the deep decarbonization of the four considered sectors. Systematic articulation among diversity of knowledge and knowledge conditions is crucial to provide cutting-edge analysis and robust scientific evidence. This will enhance the social and cultural robustness of the generated knowledge, i.e. knowledge that can be understood, processed and applied by all parties involved (Nowotny et al., 2001), and knowledge accounting for uncertainties and the ambiguities linked to it (Vilsmäier, 2008)

The heuristic of the four principles formulated by Norström et al. can help with categorizing the particular challenges that a collaborative knowledge production strategy faces when applied at global levels of governance. This can be done by shifting the attention to the 'gaps' or the 'divides' that need to be bridged in order to fulfil those principles:

Scales and levels: This challenge refers to the multiplicity of scales at which sustainability problems can be addressed, as well as the hierarchical organization (levels) of both ecological and social systems. Moreover, it points also at the complexity of those systems, which implies reciprocal interactions between levels, while – at the same time – each level features more or less independent logics and principles (Cash et al. 2006; Shrivastava et al. 2020)

Epistemic: This challenge refers to the differences in the way that knowledge is generated and interpreted in each discipline and profession, which includes differences in terminology, methods, assumptions as well as metrics that are applied to define, represent and tackle a problem or situation (Jahn, Bergmann, and Keil 2012; Blythe et al. 2017).

Norms and values: Developing a mutual understanding about the overarching goal of a governance process implies the attempt for closing the gaps between the normative systems among the actors involved in the situation; i.e. the set of conceptions about what is preferred or desirable (values) and about the legitimate means of pursuing valued ends (norms) (Scott 2001). Such normative systems vary across the several ways that individuals affiliate to social groups, such as nationality, social class, organization, ethnicity, gender, etc.. Reflecting on this particular challenge, Lawrence et al. (2022) highlight the importance of promoting the foregrounding explicit of norms and values of participants “to ensure that space for ongoing reflection and dialogue is embedded in the process”.

Organisational: achieving appropriate levels of involvement requires bridging the different logics or ways in which organizations manage the activities of the actors affiliated to them. Because from a sociological perspective, one central feature of organizations is that things and people are considered as resources that are allocated in order to achieve specific purposes, which in turn contribute to build consistency and stability to the organization (Scott 2001). Bridging these organizational divides has been identified as a crucial challenge in the standard literature on transdisciplinary research (Lawrence et al. 2022; Biermann et al. 2019). In collaboration processes that should involve actors across several scales and levels of governance, this challenge can be expected to be even stronger.

The Sectoral Conversations are conceived as a series of sector-specific transdisciplinary mutual learning formats among a small, but targeted and carefully selected group of researchers and external stakeholders within a sectoral system that co-produce knowledge and builds relationships over the project lifetime. The Sectoral Conversations enable us to combine interdisciplinary work with deep stakeholder involvement throughout the entire project. They provide a space to explore the complementarities and contradictions of different disciplinary perspectives. A focus will be put on the triangulation of results from the various research inputs coming from the project (see below).

Triangulation

Triangulation is commonly understood as the application of different methods, approaches, or perspectives on the same or a very similar issue with a view to mutually validate research results. This approach can also be described as ‘triangulation for convergence’. However, triangulation may also be used to broaden the understanding of the subject – ‘triangulation for complementarity’ (Huntington et al., 2004). Finally, ‘triangulation for divergence’ can be employed to “reveal the mismatches between scales of knowledge of the actors, i.e., scientists, government officials, and citizens, involved” (Ahlborg & Nightingale, 2012, p. 16).

Decarbonization narrative

The project wanting to undertake the Sectoral Conversations will contain different epistemic divides, as explained above in section 2.2. The “Conceptual Clarification” exercise, see section 4, was used to building agreement on the meaning and use of concepts. Here we share the example of the concept “decarbonization”. This concept was selected for that exercise because of its relevance for advancing the objectives of supporting transformative dynamics towards the deep decarbonization of the four considered sectors. This section reports on: (a) issues in which common understanding among the participant researchers was apparent, (b) issues that remained unclear or controversial, and (c) the roles that decarbonization narratives can have in the different research strands.

Decarbonization narratives can be understood as stories that describe how deep reductions in the GHG emissions of a sectoral system could be achieved. These stories are built of elements such as:

- › The **drivers** of current emissions as well as of potential reductions
- › The **conditions** that determine the current performance of the sectoral systems as well as the possibilities for inducing changes towards decarbonizing them
- › The **actors** that are key in order to advance the transformation of the sectoral systems and/or that would result particularly affected by the transformation

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- › The **strategies** that those actors can apply in order to effectively advance the decarbonization of the sectoral systems
- › The (additional) **impacts** that the envisioned transformation might bring about to societies and economies in general; i.e. effects (positive and negative) beyond the reduction of GHG emissions.

Unclear or controversial issues

Three issues appear of relevance for characterizing what “decarbonization narratives” are, but remained unclear or controversial after the conceptual clarification exercise:

- › Differentiation to other types of ‘stories’: Other terms such as ‘storylines’, ‘pathways’ and ‘scenarios’ are commonly used in academic and political debates on climate mitigation. All those terms also refer to ways of ‘telling stories’ about how climate mitigation can look like in the future. The scope of the exercise did not allow for exploring the differences and relations among those other types of ‘story-telling’.
- › The purpose: One approach is to understand decarbonization narratives as a methodological tool that can facilitate the articulation and integration of results from different strands of analysis. For instance, by providing consistency and coherence in the assumptions set for different types of analysis. On the other hand, decarbonization narratives can be understood as tools for facilitating the transfer of the results of the research to a broad range of (non-academic) audiences . For instance, by translating results emanating from complex sets of assumptions, models and/or analyses into rather straightforward stories about the decarbonization process.
- › Multiplicity: Given the different system boundaries that are being considered by the different research strands(i.e. sectors, national states, geographical regions) it can be expected that the elements of the stories about their transformations can vary from one system to the other.

Roles in the analytical processes

Some of the unclear or controversial issues found during the conceptual clarification exercise point at two usages or roles that decarbonization narratives can have in different research strands of the project.

- › Inputs for the research process: Decarbonization narratives can be understood as qualitative descriptions of *plausible* future developments of the sectoral systems. In this way, they can provide a starting point for deriving and/or underpinning specific assumptions and parameters needed to run the analysis of those plausible futures. This role of decarbonization narratives as inputs for the research process is characteristic of analysis comprising quantitative modelling and simulation methods.

- › Outputs from the research process: Decarbonization narratives can be also understood as qualitative descriptions of how the transformation process of sectoral systems can be expected to take place. In this vein, they can serve as formats for elaborating theories of changes that synthesize insights derived from diverse types of sources and analyses. This kind of usage can be particularly interesting for combining insights from existing evidence (e.g., on the transformation effects of policy instruments or technical innovations) with quantitative and qualitative projections of future trajectories.

Gender Responsiveness

Gender mainstreaming is the (re)organization, improvement, development and evaluation of policy processes, so that a gender equality perspective is incorporated in all policies, at all levels and at all stages, by the actors normally involved in policymaking.

The Sectoral Conversations take into account gender-responsiveness by systematically applying the seven gender dimensions of the problem oriented ex-ante gender impact assessment (GIA) (Spitzner, 2021b) as categories of analysis in the technical context of sectors and of country-specific data collection and climate policies analysis.

Climate Relevance of Gender

Gender-based inequalities are of high relevance for climate policy in many respects. Initial discussions have revealed the important role of various gender-related aspects for sectoral workstreams.

For the transport sector, a lack of political engagement with potential violations of respectful limitations / deficiency of self-determination is particularly pertinent. Unfortunately, existing statistical data is biased towards androcentrism. E.g., no (time series of) data is available on what proportion of car purchases and uses are the result of potential structural masculine violence in public space. However, “assaultive masculinity” dominating public spaces is considered to be highly relevant in terms of car purchase and use and respective emissions, including with respect to preferences for SUVs.

The buildings sector is the sector which addresses the location of the care economy, where conditions for the gendered care economy and care work are determined. Therefore, the buildings sector is particularly relevant to gender.² Policy instruments that, e.g., do not guarantee rights of tenants to access affordable energy-saving rental housing, but instead increase energy prices, directly reduce the available income of households and thereby the budget for the care economy. Such instruments also disproportionately impact low-income households, not only because they affect a higher share of their income, but also because low-income households generally can only afford to live in less energy-efficient buildings. Households led by single mothers and female retirees make up disproportionately high shares of low-income households; energy price increases therefore typically exacerbate gender-based inequalities. Tax reliefs similarly exacerbate gender-based

² Androcentrism tends to separate products or physis from their social, societal and gender contexts, also in constructing its term and categories; even though the care economy is the basis of society and households are the economies' primary economic actors, the care economy is not classified as an economic sector in standard terminologies, and households' economic activities are divided up among the buildings and transport sectors.

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inequalities. As unpaid care and reproductive work is mostly undertaken by women while paid work is mostly undertaken by men, tax reliefs disproportionately benefit men, substantially endangering the potential for self-determination, freedom from dependence on men, and independent livelihood.

Finally, energy-intensive industries feature a particularly high prevalence of gender-based divisions of labour. Women are often precluded from access to secure and well-paid jobs in industries and related service sectors, while having to shoulder the major share of unpaid domestic care work (UNIDO, 2019). In particular moving to a circular economy entails opportunities for increasing industrial employment of women, but it also entails risks of increasing workloads for societally gender-hierarchically organized domestic care work, for example by the need to dispose of waste in a way that enables reuse and recycling (Pla-Julián & Guevara, 2019). Schultz (1993) demonstrated, studying empirically waste management contexts, that unrevised androcentric environmental policies engage in a high degree of "feminization of environmental responsibility". The same was proved in the global economy context (Wichterich, 1993) as well as for the transport sector (Spitzner, 2005; Spitzner & Beik, 1995). Therefore, the principle of explicit precaution against feminization of climate responsibility has been elevated to an essential component of sustainable, thus gender responsible climate sector policies.

Generic Process of the Sectoral Conversations

The Sectoral Conversations are conceived as a series of sector-specific transdisciplinary mutual learning formats amongst a small, but targeted and carefully selected group of researchers and external stakeholders within a sectoral system that co-produce knowledge and builds relationships over the project lifetime.

Figure 1: Pert-diagram of the Sectoral Conversations.

For each conversation cycle, we will go through three phases:

- › **Preparation:** Identify the purpose and objectives for the conversation cycle and select adequate engagement methods to achieve those objectives. Logistical preparation.
- › **Sectoral conversation encounter:** In order to maintain a high level of engagement also between the main events of the Sectoral Conversations, it will be required to engage with the participants regularly to ensure continuous communication, to solicit feedback in order to improve the participant experience in subsequent iterations, and to manage participants' expectations.

- › **Digest and reflection of the sectoral conversation:** The objective of this stage is to facilitate the exploitation of the insights emerging from the Sectoral Conversations. This will include a project internal debrief of each conversation cycle involving all relevant sectoral experts involved with a view to drawing specific conclusions on what is relevant for each of them. These insights will be documented and included in subsequent versions of the PDD. The documentation will (1) specify substantive lessons learned; (2) identify needs to adjust/refine research questions, assumptions, or research design; and (3) identify key insights that have emerged, which contribute to new knowledge and may be of interest to sector stakeholders and national policymakers in the context of NDC and LTS development. Moreover, this stage will also include a debriefing of the process of the previous conversation engagement. On the basis of this reflection, the purpose and objectives as well as the engagement methods for the subsequent conversation cycle will be refined and updated.

Figure 2: Illustration of the Sectoral Conversations work flow.

We take note that one of the downsides of the sectoral approach proposed and implemented in the sectoral conversations is a risk to overlook cross-sectoral implications. The four sectors in focus are not independent of each other but coupled either directly or via the energy conversion sector. This sector coupling relates for example to the role of biomass produced in the AFOLU sector but used as a construction material in the building sector, a feedstock in the pulp and paper or even plastics industry, or a fuel in the energy conversion sector. In order to not lose track of those sector couplings, the debrief and digest of the sectoral conversations will explicitly also consider ways in which the discussed mitigation strategies and options could have ripple effects each of the other sectors as well as major implications for the energy conversion sector.

Groundwork: the development of the Conversation's Process Design Document

To have a fruitful conversation, it is required to start by outlining options and discussing the motivation and proposed design of the Sectoral Conversation across the three cycles. The Process Design Document (PDD) has been designed as a key instrument to support this thinking process. It can be found attached in Annex 1.

Completing the PDD will certainly imply the need to narrow down the scope of the sectoral conversation to a limited number of specific transformation challenges and/or specific challenges

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and opportunities. This discussion of pros and cons for different options should be a process, involving different people at different levels, with the final details of the design being decided and agreed upon by the community gathered at the first conversation encounter. When preparing the first session, it is critical to achieve a balance between concrete propositions (to have a solid foundation for discussions) and openness (to allow participants to choose *their* topic and develop the necessary ownership). To prepare the ground for this choice of focus, a pre-scoping exercise is recommended (see Pre-scoping section below).

The PDD is intended to be a living document that will be iteratively updated. After each sectoral conversation encounter, we will reflect on the outcome, both with respect to the content of the discussions and the process and functioning of the group. These reflections will also be documented in the PDD.

Building on the lessons and insights from the first (or second) conversation cycle, we will revise and specify the planning for subsequent conversation cycles and record those plans in updated versions of the PDD. That way, the PDD serves as the central place for documenting the sectoral conversations.

For the initial development of the PDD, two main considerations are worth noting as part of the groundwork.

Building the sectoral conversation community

The selection of stakeholders that will be included in each of the sectoral conversation communities should first and foremost be aligned with the ultimate goal of the Sectoral Conversation. Matching the desirable outcome of the conversation and the actors that are required to reach this goal is a central and iterative process of the development (and further refinement) of the PDD. Moreover, there are a number of guiding principles that should inform the selection of stakeholders in accordance with the terms described in the project proposal. These are described below.

Sectoral Conversation participants shall be selected to (1) facilitate the exploitation of the newly generated knowledge in the NDCs and LTS national processes and in the Global Stocktake (representation of national policymakers and key policy influencers); (2) cater for the transdisciplinary nature of the knowledge co-produced (representation of key stakeholders that are directly affected and have the capacity to act as change agents within their respective sectoral systems); (3) provide good geographic representation from the targeted countries. Gender balance and gender-related expertise will also be considered in the built-up of this community.

The Sectoral Conversations will flexibly include face-to-face workshops as well as ongoing decentralized engagement through e.g. online meetings, e-mail exchanges or other innovative remote meeting options. To ensure a high degree of engagement and building of trust, we aim for **~15 participants** for each Sectoral Conversation as well as continuous involvement of the same experts across all main encounters. Depending on the evolution of the discussions, additional stakeholders or specialized experts may be invited to join the group.

Pre-scoping

The pre-scoping should help sector leads in the choice of focus by integrating views of colleagues and external experts on the most recent developments and testing general appetite for further work on a specific topic/sub-sector/issue.

The talks with external stakeholders will help understand the interest and demand for discussion on specific areas within the real-world actors, as well as identifying synergies and overlaps with other relevant initiatives. It will also be an important occasion to map networks and relationships to assess the possibility of reaching out to certain stakeholders. In fact, the capacity to convene the most relevant actors for a certain discussion will also determine the choice of focus for that conversation.

The talks with the project colleagues will provide invaluable insight on the most critical focus areas per sector based on research undertaken to date. These exchanges will be most useful to understand the capacity to provide relevant research to a certain question, particularly noting the multidisciplinary nature of the team. The objective is to appraise where we can bring the best value in the face of numerous challenges and gaps that need to be overcome to achieve the structural transformations underpinning the Paris-compatible pathways.

These exploratory exchanges are the responsibility of the sector conversation leads. Below, we offer some ideas on how they could be organized. The PDD document also includes a proposed framework to capture the outputs of this “Pre-scoping” exercise.

Consultations with external stakeholders

- › Select a set of 4-6 external experts and/or sector stakeholders
 - › These interviews do not need to follow academic conventions. It may be just an informal structured dialogue.
 - › Consider a balance of perspectives: i.e., private, policy, civil society, as well as national and multinational levels
- › Structure in a consistent way the inputs of the stakeholder, for instance, according to challenges and solutions:
 - › The main challenges of the sector in order to move towards a deep decarbonization
 - › Relevant decarbonization options (e.g., technologies, policies, infrastructural changes, investments, behavioural/demand patterns) for advancing the deep decarbonization of the sector
- › Procure a traceable output:
 - › Summarizing notes of each talk

Consultations within the project

Specific consultations and exchanges with colleagues are recommended, particularly to cover in depth expectations and/or needs. This may also take the form of a short online survey . This could include the following generic questions, or any specific question the sector leads may have in mind:

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- › Based on existing knowledge: 1) Main critical deep decarbonization challenges, 2) Key components for deep decarbonization pathways (options) and 3) Critical “boundary condition” or enablers
- › For planned research: What are the key insights and/or assumptions of your research work that you would like to be discussed/triangulated by real-world stakeholders? (Besides challenges and options), that might help to set the scene of the conversation?

The results may be structured according to the subjects mentioned (e.g., specific decarbonization challenges, decarbonization strategies or options, or related aspects). It may also be pertinent to highlight particular points of divergence/conflict arising from the interviews/survey.

Engagement Methods Toolkit

In this section, a selection of engagement methods are presented and described that could be used to facilitate discussion in the Sectoral Conversations. The Sectoral Leads may decide whether to use these methods and – if necessary – adapt them to their specific needs.

Conceptual clarification

Conceptual clarification is a method that aims at building agreement on the meaning and use of concepts, among a group of individuals that represent and/or enact different disciplines or expertises within a transdisciplinary research group.

“Concepts are mental symbols, the units of thought.” (Carey, 2011) Concepts are the essential building blocks of the descriptions, explanations and/or theories that any discipline or profession uses and processes in order to build valid statements about the behavior of the empirical world they focus on. Two features of concepts are particularly important to consider when advancing collaborative research. (a) The actual ‘content’ or ‘meaning’ of concepts: Concepts can be understood as mental representations of entities or phenomena that we observe, perceive and/or pretend to apprehend. (b) The relation between concepts (as mental symbols) with terms (i.e. linguistic symbols): This implies on the one hand that concepts (and the entities they represent) are linked to ‘labels’ (words) and on the other hand that most of the operations we undertake with concepts (like thinking, explaining or speaking) are facilitated by the use of language.

One central differentiation among disciplines (and among professions) is that they develop their own set of concepts, explanations and theories in rather autonomous ways. Therefore, in settings of collaborative research there is not any guarantee for the convergence among the relations between concepts (mental representations) and actual meanings applied by the different disciplines and professions involved, even in the case (or particularly when) the same terms (words, linguistic symbols) are used. This can be critical in the case of concepts that are central for the definition of the research endeavour; for instance in the case of notions that are key for building the problem definition, the objectives, the guiding questions and/or the framing of the research. Clarifying those differences and agreeing on ways to deal with them is particularly important in the early stages of the research process (Bergmann et al., 2012).

Three Horizons

The Three Horizons Dialogue framework (Sharpe et al., 2016) is a tool to engage a diverse group of stakeholders in a structured collective imagining/visioning exercise. Its key strength is to integrate diverse perspectives and to enable a constructive way forward even when competing or contradicting views are assembled in the group.

The method is particularly useful as a brainstorming tool for initiating the Sectoral Conversations. However, it can also be used in a more in-depth way, guiding an entire scenario-development workshop. In the Sectoral Conversations this method could be used on the occasion of the first encounter as it enables the group to quickly establish a common ground from which decisions for the direction of future deliberations in the group can be taken.

Futures Wheel

The purpose of the futures wheel method is to assess possible implications of proposed changes in a systematic and holistic way. Starting from an assumption about future change, a first order of direct effects is explored. Then second and subsequently third order ripple effects are also considered. That way, a group of experts can relatively quickly grasp anticipated implications (good or bad) for any proposed action.

In the context of the Sectoral Conversations, this method is particularly apt to interrogate proposed solutions (decarbonization strategies and associated policies and measures) and their respective technical, social, economic and political/institutional implications. This method can be recommended for the second round of sectoral conversations.

Annex 3: Process Design Document (PDD) Template

The aim of the Process Design Document (PDD) is to outline the scope, affected stakeholders, format and sequence (types of inputs and outputs per engagement) and exact approach and methods to address the sectoral idiosyncrasies. We have to understand the PDD as a living document that will also help refine the Sectoral Conversation methodology over the different iterations.

Background of the sector

Please include here a short description of the sector

Pre-scoping synthesis

This synthesis should describe the main takeaways from the scoping phase exchanges with both external and project-internal experts.

A proposed framework is presented below for reporting the main takeaways, but sector leads may adapt it as necessary.

Key issues related to the challenges for deep decarbonization in this sector

>
>
>

Key issues related to decarbonization options/solutions/opportunities for the sector:

>
>
>

Key issues related to boundary conditions and international enablers:

>
>
>

Particularly divergent or controversial aspects:

>
>
>

Other important aspects highlighted by the stakeholders:

>
>
>

Outlining the purpose of the sectoral conversation

The Sectoral Conversation to be established will help integrate disciplinary knowledge within the project and connect the research with the empirical realities of the sector. This will enhance the relevance, robustness and credibility of the research outputs. Moreover, in order to achieve the specific impact objectives of the project, the Sectoral Conversations should be considered a social process in itself where the generated dialogue has the potential to result in (either) facilitating upcoming decisions, buy-in and support of key leaders or change agents or learning. Participants of this dialogue should be able to directly benefit from the encounter, and therefore, have a specific interest in taking part of this.

Process and outcome intended by the different rounds of sectoral conversations, by answering the following questions:

- > What are conditions, elements and actors necessary to achieve that transformation?
- > Which actor(s) or condition(s) can be influenced by the knowledge to be generated in this project?
- > What/Who will make the targeted actor(s) engage with the specific intervention?
- > How to successfully manage the engagement to try to guarantee a successful outcome?

The following table should help outline the purpose of the Sectoral Conversation over the three cycles and the strategy that will likely deliver the desired impact.

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Targeted transformation: What key (physical, institutional, political) structural transformations are we targeting to enable deep decarbonization in this sector?	...	Based on sector lead know-how of detailed sectoral pathways to achieve deep decarbonization across relevant geographies (Tier 1 and Tier 2). Main options can be obtained/confirmed through the pre-scoping consultations.
Targeted lever of change: What are conditions, elements and actors' position necessary to achieve the targeted transformation?	...	Based on sector lead know-how of the analysis of the outcome of current policies and measures, existing gaps and opportunities to achieve deep decarbonization across relevant geographies (Tier 1 and Tier 2). Main options can be obtained/confirmed through the pre-scoping consultations.
Type of desirable outcome of the dialogue generated through the Sectoral Conversations:	<i>Choose one:</i> A. Facilitating upcoming decisions thanks to creating conditions for change B. Support of key leaders or change agents thanks to enhanced credibility and legitimacy C. Learning to understand what changes are necessary	Based on sector lead and Consortium understanding of the implications of the targeted change for specific actors, and for the actor(s) or condition(s) that can be influenced over the project lifetime by knowledge generated within the Consortium.
Description of the tactics: how can the dialogue be structured to achieve such outcome? How does the research produced by the Consortium feed this Conversation?		
Key actors / stakeholders: who has the capacity to play a role for this targeted lever of change? Who are the affected stakeholders?		

Building the sectoral conversation community

Sectoral conversation (project internal) community

	Name of contact(s)	Email address
Qualitative analysis		
Quantitative analysis		

Stakeholder Mapping

Collect suggestions of external experts that the “project internal community”, especially the sectoral experts, consider could contribute to the purpose of the Sectoral Conversation as described in the Section 3 table. Of the suggestions collected, you will have to decide on a selection that represents the diversity of the sector.

The selection of participants will seek to cover a wide range of stakeholders in terms of geographic diversity and constituencies (policymakers, public administration, academia, industry, finance sector, civil society) as well as different sub-sectors/ industries represented as appropriate.

Once chosen, you can list them below:

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Private sector

Expert	Organization	email	Who can facilitate the contact?	Short assessment on relevance or potential contribution

Policymaking

Expert	Organization	email	Who can facilitate the contact?	Short assessment on relevance or potential contribution

Civil society and academia

Expert	Organization	email	Who can facilitate the contact?	Short assessment on relevance or potential contribution

Planning the sectoral conversation

	Purpose & Objectives	Engagement methods & tools
Conversation cycle 1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Agree on the rules of the game: how much public/ private, how to include people, how to communicate > Cement the mandate of the stakeholder: what they can expect, what is the agreed outcome of this community > To identify next steps > Others 	
Conversation Cycle 2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > 	
Conversation Cycle 3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > > Exploring options for exploitation after the end of the project 	

The Sectoral Conversations, with hindsight

- > **Conversation cycle 1**
 - > Results/reflexions
 - > Content related
 - > Process related
- > **Conversation cycle 2**
 - > Results/reflexions
 - > Content related
 - > Process related
- > **Conversation cycle 3**
 - > Results/reflexions
 - > Content related
 - > Process related
- > **Exploitation**

PARTICIPANTS

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